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Barriers to Accessing the Ontario Autism Program

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Barriers to Accessing the Ontario Autism Program

by

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Thesis

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Statement of Originality

I affirm that this research paper is entirely my own work, and no part of it has been previously published or submitted for publication elsewhere. This document represents the final version of my research, incorporating revisions approved by my Major Research Project committee. It has not been submitted to any other academic institution for a higher degree. I confirm that I have not sought assistance from external sources, except in accordance with the guidelines provided by my instructor and outlined in the Thesis/Major Research Project Guidebook.

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Abstract

In 2018, the Ontario government announced changes to the service delivery and funding model for autism services. These changes aimed to eliminate the waitlist and provide caregivers with control over services for their children (up to age 18), diagnosed with an autism spectrum disorder (ASD). When this research started, over 50,000 children were waiting for needs-based funding. This study sought to identify any obstacles to services by asking caregivers to share what they experienced when accessing publicly funded services offered through the Ontario Autism Program (OAP). Access to early intervention services and timely access to support were significant barriers, with caregivers citing long wait times and insufficient support as the most frustrating obstacles.

Keywords: Autism, caregivers, government programs, social services, barriers, Ontario, OAP

Dedication

I want to extend my sincere gratitude to my professors and classmates at Adler Graduate Professional School. Through their unwavering support, guidance, and adaptability, we completed our studies during the global pandemic. I am especially thankful to Dr. Rosemary Young and Dr. James Porter for their invaluable expertise and encouragement throughout the development of this thesis. Last but not least, I dedicate this work to my family and friends, who patiently listened to me talk about my thesis for far too long. Your enduring support was a constant source of strength, and I truly could not have done this without you. I love and appreciate you all.

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Chapter 1: Introduction to the Study

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by impairments in communication, deficits in social and play skills and restrictive and repetitive patterns of behaviour. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) identifies the following diagnostic criteria for ASD:

- A. Persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction across multiple contexts.
 - B. Restricted, repetitive patterns of behaviour, interests, or activities.
 - C. Symptoms must be present in the early developmental period (but may not fully manifest until social demands exceed limited capacities or may be masked by learned strategies in later life).
 - D. Symptoms cause clinically significant impairment in social, occupational, or other important areas of current functioning.
 - E. These disturbances are not better explained by intellectual disability (intellectual developmental disorder) or global developmental delay.
- (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

Autism is a neurodevelopmental disorder that affects all cultures, ethnicities, races and gender identities (Autism Ontario, 2018). According to the 2018 report from the National Autism Spectrum Disorder Surveillance System (NASS), the prevalence of ASD in children aged 5-17 years was 1 in 66. In other words, about 1- 2% of the Canadian population meets the criteria for autism spectrum disorder (ASD), and there are approximately 135,000 individuals with autism in Ontario (Autism Ontario, 2018).

Applied Behaviour Analysis (ABA) and specifically Early Intensive Behavioural Intervention (EIBI) are evidence-based treatments that can help remediate some of the symptoms associated with autism with clinically significant outcomes (Lovaas, 1987; Perry et al, 2008; Solish & Perry, 2008; Granpeesheh et al., 2009). Cooper, Heron and Heward (2007) defined applied behaviour analysis as “the science in which tactics derived from the principles of behavior are applied to improve socially significant behavior, and experimentation is used to identify the variables responsible for the improvement in behavior” (p.690). EIBI typically “consists of 20-40 hours per week of individualized instruction for children with autism who begin treatment at the age of 4 years or younger and who usually continue for 2-3 years” (Association for Science in Autism Treatment, 2020).

The initial Autism Intervention Program (AIP) was introduced in 1999 and provided E/IBI to children 6 years of age and under who were assessed by a clinician during intake to be on the moderate to severe end of the spectrum. It should be noted that the author of this study uses the terms EIBI and IBI interchangeably. Following a court challenge in early 2000, the age-cap and severity criteria were removed. Under this program, families were given a choice between a direct service option (DSO) and a direct funding option (DFO). Most children received 12-27 hours per week of EIBI (beginning therapy before age 6 and over 20 hours per week for at least a year) or ABA (e.g., fewer hours, older children) therapy. DFO and DSO services were typically provided on weekdays (school hours) with greater flexibility for after-school and weekends if caregivers chose the direct funding option.

In a 2008 file review of 332 children who were in the previous Autism Intervention Program (AIP), Perry et al. reported that approximately 50% of children improved in terms of autism severity. Almost two-thirds demonstrated clinically significant improvement in their cognitive levels (12 months or more of their “mental age”), and the overall rate of development for the group reviewed almost doubled. Another study in Ontario found that high-quality IBI, for two years or longer at a very young age, changed some children's developmental trajectory, such that they narrowed the age equivalent gap (Perry et al, 2011).

The AIP program had its challenges, with waitlists averaging over two and a half years. Children began receiving IBI or ABA well past 6 years old (Piccininni & Penner, 2016). Like the findings of the Pay Now or Pay Later report, Piccininni and Penner (2016) found that expanding the autism program and funding more IBI would not only have more favourable outcomes for those children but also increase their independence in the future. Children who receive early intervention will require less support than adults and, consequently, will “reduce the cost burden from provincial and societal perspectives (Piccininni & Penner, 2016).”

A provincial election in Ontario in 2018 resulted in a change in government, and the AIP was discontinued. The waitlist at that time consisted of approximately 23,000 children, and the government pledged to eliminate the waitlist within 18 months (Crawley, 2019). Within the new Ontario Autism Program (OAP), children selected from the waitlist received a yearly allotment based on age. Annually, caregivers were given \$20,000-\$22,000 if their child was 6 and under or \$3000 to \$5500 per year for those

seven to seventeen. Caregivers protested this as unfair, advocating for a needs-based system. The OAP was modified to a hybrid age and need-based system. While awaiting this service, some children on the waitlist before April 2021 were eligible for one or two installments of the age-based funding noted above, called interim one-time funding and a one-time funding renewal. When the funding by age model was revised to needs-based, each caregiver had to complete an extensive intake interview online or on the phone, answering questions about their child's abilities, sometimes for hours. This process was called a determination of needs (DON). Based on the caregiver responses to the questions asked by the worker during the DON interview, each child was eligible for a maximum of \$65,000 annually. Children in the previous AIP were gradually transferred to the new OAP, and depending on the date of transfer, they may have initially received the age-based funding, followed by the DON budget up to \$65,000, depending on the child's age and caregiver responses to the DON interview questions.

In 2020, the OAP introduced Foundational Family Services, which were also offered to any child with an OAP number. These services included workshops, brief and targeted consultations, mentoring, resource sharing, and transition supports. Service models varied across the province, with some agencies offering in-person at a clinic, others online, and some in the home (Ontario Ministry of Children, Community and Social Services, August 2020, Ontario Autism Program: foundational family services, overview and services para. 2 and 1).

In 2021, the OAP introduced Caregiver-Mediated Early Years (C-MEY) for children on the waitlist who were 4 or under. These programs were intended to help

caregivers support their child's development in the areas most impacted by autism (social interaction, play, communication, emotional development and adaptive development). Coaching was provided by professionals like behaviour therapists, speech and language pathologists and occupational therapists (Ontario Ministry of Children, Community and Social Services, June 2021, Ontario Autism Program: caregiver-mediated early years programs, Overview, para. 2).

The Entry-to-School (ETS) program was another service offered to children on the waitlist entering school. Children up to age 6 who are starting school for the first time are eligible for this invitation-only OAP program. This program was offered half days over a six to twelve-month period and focused on developing the child's communication, play skills, school readiness, functional routines/self-help, behaviour management, pre-academics, learning and attention (Ontario Ministry of Children, Community and Social Services, January 2022, Ontario Autism Program: entry to school program, Overview, para. 2)

In 2022, Urgent Response Services (URS) were made available to children engaging in escalating safety-related behaviours. URS was a brief service (no more than twelve weeks), typically provided in person at the child's home. It was intended to stabilize, not eliminate, behaviours that were a safety concern, such as self-injury and elopement (Ontario Ministry of Children, Community and Social Services, March 2022, Ontario Autism Program: urgent response services, Overview and Eligibility, para. 1 and 2).

The price of a needs-based ABA/EIBI therapy can be costly. Children with level one autism (what was once called high-functioning autism or Asperger's) may require more targeted, less intense services. In contrast, those with level two or three autism (moderate to severe end of the spectrum) require more diverse, intensive and specialized supports. In 2006, the cost of IBI in Ontario was estimated to be between \$40,000 and \$75,000 per child per year, depending on the number of hours and other factors like intensity or support needs (Motiwala et al., 2006). For 15 to 20 hours of one-to-one treatment per week, ABA can cost \$48,000 to \$63,000 per year (Gurney, 2019).

The high cost associated with therapy is well below the financial support required for older children and adults with autism who do not receive treatment. In 2007, a study in Texas estimated that providing three years of EIBI to children would save that state "\$208,500 per child across eighteen years of special education (Chasson et al., 2007)." In the United States, annual estimates for residential services can be \$60,000 to \$128,00 per year compared to the cost of IBI for preschool-age children, which was between \$40,000 to \$60,000 (Amaral et al., 2011). Here in Canada, a 2014 paper by Dudley and Emery estimated that the lifetime costs associated with caring for an individual with ASD who required intense supports were approximately 5.5 million dollars (Dudley & Emery, 2014).

In 2007, the Senate Committee on Social Affairs, Science and Technology published *Pay Now or Pay Later: Autism Families in Crisis*. This report identified key gaps in access to and wait times for service, as well as inadequate disability supports, which created increased stressors (financial and emotional) for families of children with

ASD. The Senate report clearly stated that the consequences of not working with the provinces to create a national autism strategy to address these deficits would create a future where the government is paying more for adult social services, welfare and institutionalization. Piccininni et al. 2017 used 2012 data to examine the cost-effectiveness of removing the waitlist entirely. At that time, the waitlist had about 1700 children and included only children 4 and under. They discovered savings of \$53,000 up to age 65, for an overall lifetime savings of \$267,000.

Although other reports have identified barriers and recommended key revisions to the Ontario Autism Program (McLaughlin & Schneider, 2019; Ontario Scientific Expert Task Force for the Treatment of Autism Spectrum Disorder [OSETT-ASD], 2017), the author of this study sought to quantify the barriers within the current OAP service model.

The Purpose of the Study

This study aimed to pinpoint and measure the challenges families face when accessing services for their child(ren) with autism within the current service delivery model, specifically the Ontario Autism Program (OAP).

Statement of the Problem

Autism diagnoses are on the rise worldwide. In 2001, the global rate was less than one in five hundred people; eight years later, the World Health Organization estimated that one in one hundred and sixty people had an autism spectrum disorder (Heifetz, 2019). Based on data collected from the 2019 Canadian Health Survey on Children and Youth, approximately 1 in 50 Canadian children and youth aged 1 to 17 have been diagnosed with an autism spectrum disorder (Statistics Canada, 2020). With the

prevalence steadily increasing, many caregivers have grown increasingly frustrated with the lack of timely and coordinated services and supports. Autism is one of the few developmental disorders that can show significant symptom remediation for some individuals who receive EIBI (Eikeseth, 2009; Eldevik, 2009, 2010; Odom, 2009; Warren, 2011). It can also require a multi-disciplinary approach for interventions, with many children on the spectrum requiring occupational, physio, speech and behavioural therapies (Granpeesheh et al., 2009). Early intervention and immediate and early access to services are key.

In 2018, the Ontario government announced changes that were intended to eliminate the waitlist and provide therapy to all children diagnosed with ASD. The waitlist at that time sat at about 23,000 children (Granpeesheh et al., 2009). These changes also included removing the direct service option and providing funding directly to each family, to give them more agency over their child's treatment. In May 2022, according to the Government of Ontario's webpage ([Ontario.ca/page/autism-ontario](https://ontario.ca/page/autism-ontario)), over 53,000 children were waiting for autism services in Ontario. The Ontario Government stopped posting current waitlist numbers; however, it is estimated that as of June 2024, approximately 73,000 children were waiting for needs-based funding (Jones, 2024).

The current model for the Ontario Autism Program (OAP) presents many challenges for many families of children diagnosed with an autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Long wait times to be assessed for autism are just the beginning; after receiving a diagnosis of ASD for their child, many caregivers are then tasked with the challenges of

securing reliable and appropriate service options. Often armed with the knowledge that early intervention is recommended and long wait times are ahead, caregivers have little time to grieve or process the diagnosis. They are immediately tasked with completing the many forms and intake interviews required to access services. These challenges can be magnified in regions where services are sparse or non-existent (e.g., remote/rural areas). For newcomers to Canada who may be unfamiliar with the system, and those who do not speak English as their first language, these processes can seem overwhelming.

Significance of the Study

Caregivers of children diagnosed with autism experience higher rates of depression and mental health challenges (Lee et al., 2019; Weiss & Lunskey, 2010; Vogan et al., 2014). The current service model of the OAP may increase stressors for these families because of the gaps in service navigation and provision. It is hoped that the results of this study will identify the specific barriers and inform decision-making so that the OAP meets the needs of all families across Ontario. Consequently, caregivers may have fewer obstacles to face and less stress when attempting to access quality services for their child(ren) in a timely and seamless fashion. The initial target of eliminating the waitlist was grand, and it would have helped many children receive evidence-based early intervention services. With a waitlist of over 73,000, most children will not receive access to needs-based/core clinical funding until they are at least 6 years old (Jones, 2024).

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Although very few studies were available specifically on the current Ontario Autism Program (OAP), there is a substantial body of research examining access to developmental, health, and mental health services in Ontario, as well as some research on the effectiveness of the previous Autism Intervention Program (AIP) in Ontario. Drawing from these resources, several themes emerged when identifying barriers to publicly funded services. These barriers, identified as important by service providers and caregivers, fall under two categories: system navigation and service provision.

In 2018, Berk et al. released a qualitative report identifying barriers to accessing mental health and addiction supports in Canada. From that report, several of the barriers identified in providing publicly funded mental health support were similar to those experienced by caregivers accessing the OAP. The first barrier identified for families accessing publicly funded supports was system navigation. Identifying who can provide services, where to go, options for service and how to apply were the most common themes (Berk et al., 2018). In a qualitative study by Minnes et al. (2018), mothers of children with ASD in Ontario cited fragmented systems and supports as a significant obstacle to service. These mothers hoped the system would become “seamless and work and support the families with the individual holistically, with a central place where you can be assessed and treated” (Minnes et al., 2018). In another study, primary care practitioners concurred that families of children with developmental, behavioural and mental health disorders were left on their own: “There is no one specialist or sector in

health, education, or social services mandated to follow children...leaving children and families to navigate complex systems of care across their lifespan” (Young et al, 2020).

With an ASD diagnosis, caregivers can complete the application online or call to request a paper copy be mailed to them. Upon completing the application and submitting the necessary paperwork, they wait to receive their child’s OAP number and, eventually, core clinical funding. An OAP number is required to access government-funded services (e.g., Foundational Family Services, Caregiver-Mediated, Urgent Response Services), but is not typically required for early intervention speech, physio and occupational therapy services.

System navigation can be challenging for those immersed in public services and health care. Usually, the family doctor is the first point of contact for many families, yet even the professionals have limited knowledge. The Primary Care Practitioners (PCPs) in Young’s 2020 study acknowledged that unfamiliarity with resources and their limited training in caring for children with developmental, mental health and behavioural disorders beyond the screening process resulted in barriers to families. Therefore, caregivers less integrated with the public service sector would have less knowledge than professionals immersed daily (White & Weiss, 2010). Even caregivers employed in social services (e.g., teachers and nurses) find it challenging to navigate services for children with ASD. White and Weiss’ study found that caregivers tended to use more informal channels (e.g., friends) to identify services and avenues of support for their child.

Caregivers of children with ASD are no strangers to advocacy, and in the study by Minnes et al. (2018), mothers stressed the importance of obtaining the proper support for their children. Identifying eligible services and supports typically rests solely on the caregiver. That, combined with the added stress of raising a child with a developmental delay, mothers of kids with ASD reported feeling isolated in the system of care (Minnes et al., 2018). Supporting caregivers is integral to supporting the child. The caregiver's positive mental view was proven to positively impact resiliency regardless of the severity of the diagnosis (Kuhaneck, 2015).

Barriers can be compounded for newcomers to Canada. Their child may not have received a screening or diagnosis in their home country, or they may be unaware that services and accommodations are available (Bhayana, 2018). When caring for a child with autism, new Canadian mothers had “Limited knowledge about how to obtain help, who could help them and what their rights were in caring for a child with autism” (Khanlou, 2014). As sole caregivers, immigrant mothers in Toronto also cited “long and complicated forms in English”, lack of professional help, time constraints, limited language skills, and lack of social support (family, friends) as additional barriers (Khanlou, 2017). In 2017, the Ontario Scientific Expert Task Force for the Treatment of Autism Spectrum Disorder (OSETT-ASD) recommended establishing clear pathways for service, a transparent waitlist process and providing early intervention to younger children with a provisional diagnosis. Similarly, the McLaughlin and Schneider report (2019) identified the need for system navigation support, support groups and family counselling.

Barriers to accessing services are vast. In the McLaughlin and Schneider report (2019), families indicated some of the following challenges with the current OAP:

- 44% of respondents indicated there was not enough funding for the ABA therapy their child needed.
- 42% identified a lack of control over the time and location of services.
- 25% felt frustrated dealing with paperwork and managing services.

Often, children with ASD require behaviour and psychological services, as well as speech and language, physiotherapy and occupational therapy. Caregivers are responsible for ensuring their children are placed on the appropriate waitlists; they must coordinate services at different times and locations within their current work or school schedules. When PCPs were asked about developmental service waitlists, one participant stated plainly, “You can’t wait for 6 months when the child is doing poorly at school, and the school isn’t on top of it as well” (Young et al., 2020).

For all Ontarians, finances can be a barrier to accessing timely treatment. In 2015, 80% of caregivers said paying out of pocket, and 77% said the province's lack of coverage posed significant barriers to treatment (Jones, 2015).

The family’s financial resources impact timely access to diagnosis and services: “If caregivers have private coverage or are willing to spend a lot of money, then the process is quick and, otherwise, it is frustrating and aggravating” (Young et al., 2020). Those unable to pay out of pocket wait longer for publicly funded services. Also, the financial strain associated with navigating services typically offered during work hours often

means one parent must reduce or give up their employment. This creates additional economic strain on the family.

This process can be even more daunting for newcomer families with limited language skills and information about our complex health system and eligibility rules. In their 2018 study, Bhayana and Bhayana identified some of the barriers new families encounter when trying to access services for their children with developmental delays, which included a lack of knowledge about our healthcare system, resources, fear of deportation and poor financial situations. These barriers can continue years later: ‘The trend indicates that immigrants to Canada are more likely to experience difficulties accessing care compared to those born in Canada, even after living here for over 10 years’ (Harrington et al., 2013). With a broad range of services (ABA, speech, occupational therapy) offered simultaneously, newcomers accessed services in different, more limited ways and later in their child’s life than non-immigrant families (Khanlou, 2017). In this same study, Khanlou found that “communication barriers made it difficult for mothers to recognize the need for several providers’/service agencies’ simultaneous involvement in providing care to their children.”

In a study with immigrant fathers of children with ASD, Khanlou (2015) found that economic issues related to employment challenges (loss of employment, inflexibility of employers in unstable jobs) and financial matters (e.g., centralized services when families live outside the city due to cheaper rent, lack of a vehicle to get to appointments).

Cofounding the barriers for these caregivers and their children.

The geographic disparity is another barrier to the OAP. For those in urban areas, services can be dispersed in different parts of the city, causing some families to rely on public transit to access appointments (Khanlou, 2014). Transportation is also a barrier in rural and northern communities, where services are often dispersed across vast geographic areas. Due to the lack of qualified professionals, rural, remote, and northern communities frequently have long waitlists for services (Harrington et al., 2013). The Canadian Mental Health Association stated, "...services are less comprehensive, available and accessible than in urban areas...with workforce recruitment and retention being one of the greatest challenges facing rural and northern Ontario."

Even when comparing southern and central Ontario, there were discrepancies between professionals and caregivers in each area, focusing on perceptions of availability, accessibility and effectiveness (White & Weiss, 2010). For all families, the time commitment required to travel to and from appointments can cause significant strain on caregivers.

The last barrier identified is the lack of alternative and culturally grounded services for Indigenous, Francophone and immigrant families. Services for Indigenous populations in remote communities are sparse. In 2017, the Ontario Scientific Expert Task Force for the Treatment of Autism Spectrum Disorder (OSETT-ASD) recommended the inclusion of Indigenous community leaders when developing guidelines for OAP service providers to provide culturally sensitive services. Prioritizing education for providers on the unique needs of Indigenous communities (e.g., intergenerational trauma, housing, and food insecurities) was highlighted. (OSETT-ASD,

2017). When examining Francophone services provided by family physicians in Ontario, Gauthier (2015) noted that “Actively offering services in French should not be the responsibility of the patient.” Francophone caregivers living in Ontario have reported significant challenges finding therapy services in French.

For new Canadians, there can be unique cultural barriers to accessing services. Language barriers and technical jargon are often challenging for caregivers whose first language is not English or French. Not realizing their child has the right to access support, immigrant mothers may not advocate for more support and can be grateful for any services being offered (Khanlou, 2017).

In some cultures, there is a stigma attached to having a child with autism. Family, friends and community members may blame the child or woman for the disability, causing social isolation and exclusion (Khanlou, 2017). Immigrant mothers reported feeling stressed and depressed in circumstances where gender roles are divided, making them solely responsible for all household duties and care of the child with autism (Khanlou, 2014). The process of migration and settlement has embedded socioeconomic constraints, language barriers, lack of social networks and acculturation challenges (Khanlou, 2014). Language, communication, complex jargon, complicated delivery systems, social differences, and lack of knowledge about the diagnosis are barriers caregivers encounter when navigating new and unfamiliar service systems (Khanlou, 2014 and 2015).

OSSET-ASD stated that the government must make “a focused effort to recruit diverse candidates, including those from Indigenous and Francophone backgrounds, by

using incentive programs similar to those for physicians.” Funding interpreters for diagnostics, registration and service navigation would begin to alleviate several barriers to service.

Chapter 3: Research Methods

Participants

Participants were required to meet specific eligibility requirements; they had to be the primary caregiver for a child (or children) who qualified for the OAP (i.e., under the age of 18, living in Ontario, and diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder) to be eligible to participate. OAP services stop at age 18; therefore, caregivers of children who were 18 or older were omitted. Because the survey was conducted online, caregivers required a basic understanding of both technology and the English language.

In total, 69 caregivers responded to the survey. A total of four respondents were excluded. One failed to answer any questions beyond the eligibility screener and consent. Two participants from Toronto were excluded: one who only completed the demographic questions and another who appeared to be answering for two children, making it impossible to distinguish between them and rendering the data unusable. Two respondents were excluded from the East due to unreliable responses. One caregiver indicated that they had not received their child's OAP number and then answered questions about services that required an OAP number. The other responded to inquiries concerning OAP services that necessitated a diagnosis after saying that their child had not received an autism diagnosis.

Survey respondents were recruited using a targeted approach. An online survey link was shared with agencies, support groups, and social media platforms (e.g., Ontario Autism Coalition, Ontario Association of Behaviour Analysts), using a targeted approach to recruit caregivers of children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Respondents were

encouraged to share the survey link with other caregivers of children with ASD (snowball sampling). This researcher chose an online survey for its ease of access, as many caregivers belong to or follow online support, advocacy, or therapy-specific services.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted according to the ethical principles outlined in the Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans, Course on Research Ethics, and received approval from the Research Ethics Board (REB) at Adler Graduate Professional School. Before participating in the survey, all respondents were provided with detailed information regarding the study's process, including the consent form and eligibility criteria. The pre-survey emphasized the voluntary nature of participation, the right to withdraw at any time without consequence, and the measures implemented to ensure the confidentiality of responses. Participants were also informed that no compensation would be provided for participating in the study.

While no personal or identifying information would be made available to this researcher, respondents were cautioned about the increased risk associated with completing the survey through Facebook Messenger, where their responses and personal data could be vulnerable when using that platform. Participants were also informed that they may experience feelings of upset or distress while completing this study. To mitigate this risk, participants were advised to discontinue participation should they feel discomfort. Resources for free crisis services were also embedded at the beginning and end of the survey, and respondents were reminded that they had the right to withdraw from the study by simply closing their browsers or not submitting their responses.

Furthermore, participants had the option to skip questions, or they could opt not to answer any questions with which they did not feel comfortable by selecting the "prefer not to say" option.

Before proceeding with the survey, the logic ensured that participants acknowledged the risks and completed the electronic consent form. The researcher provided respondents with comprehensive information about the research project, including the risks and benefits, their right to ask questions of the researcher or their supervisors, and confirmation that their participation was completely voluntary. After the consent process, respondents completed an eligibility screener to ensure they met the eligibility criteria: being a caregiver to a child (under 18 years old) diagnosed with autism, residing in Ontario, and being comfortable reading and responding to questions in English.

Several measures were implemented to ensure the confidentiality of participant data. After download, case numbers were assigned to each participant, and all potential identifiers, such as IP addresses, were removed. This process was conducted to ensure that the data could not be traced back to individual participants. All data collected was securely stored on a password-encrypted USB drive, which was kept in a secure location. Data were presented in aggregate form to protect the respondents' anonymity further, and any direct quotes were paraphrased to prevent identification of the source.

Data Collection Methods

The link to the survey was shared with agencies and support groups, who distributed it online to their subscribers. The online survey (hosted on SurveyMonkey)

was accessible to participants from September 23, 2023, to December 23, 2023. The data collection period was extended beyond the initial 30-day timeframe due to a delay in receiving approval from one agency to share the research. This extension was necessary to ensure that all potential participants had a fair chance to respond to the survey, despite the delay in approval.

The survey aimed to identify the barriers encountered by families when navigating services for their children with autism. The survey questions were developed based on the literature review described in the previous chapter and were designed to quantify the barriers caregivers experienced when accessing the OAP. Survey questions asked caregivers to share their experiences about service access (e.g., wait and travel times) and provision (satisfaction with funding and therapy). The survey also collected information on participants' geographic location to explore potential variations in regional barriers, the amount of personal funds expended on services (to assess financial strain) and their overall satisfaction with the services.

The research questions underwent an extensive review process for content and clarity by five professionals in the field and two caregivers of children with autism. This comprehensive review process ensured that the questions were designed to capture the most common challenges reported by caregivers of children with special needs. Using the literature reviewed and the input provided by professional service providers and caregivers, the survey questions were structured to be straightforward and aimed to capture the most frequently reported challenges when navigating the system and accessing services.

The final survey consisted of 55 questions, including 40 predetermined items (e.g., multiple-choice, yes/no, Likert scales) and 13 open-ended questions (e.g., program strengths, date of registration, age at diagnosis), which allowed caregivers to type in their responses. The remaining three open-ended questions at the end of the survey specifically asked caregivers for their opinions on the strengths of the OAP, the most significant barriers they encountered and any other relevant information they wished to share. To enhance the relevance of the survey for each respondent, embedded skip logic directed caregivers past questions that were not applicable based on their experiences with specific service streams or funding types. For instance, caregivers whose children had not received funding automatically moved to subsequent questions unrelated to funding. The reason for excluding participants who had not received a specific service or funding was to ensure that the data collected were from caregivers who had direct experience with the services being evaluated.

All 65 respondents could answer questions about their demographics (e.g., geographic area, their relationship to the child with autism), their experiences obtaining a diagnosis, registering for the OAP, out-of-pocket expenses, and using translation services. Similarly, all respondents could answer questions about SLP, OT and PT services. Although these services are not provided through the OAP, most are available through early intervention and preschool outreach programs and are an essential part of many children's treatment needs. The open-ended questions about the most significant barriers, strengths and other thoughts on the OAP were also available to all.

With a modest sample size of 65 respondents compared to over 73,000 families waiting (representing less than 1% of potential caregivers whose children are waiting for OAP service), inferences could not be drawn about the broader population. The range in responses to Likert scale items and quantitative data (e.g., wait times, diagnosis) indicated high response variability. Furthermore, less than half of those who responded reported receiving funding, and an even smaller number reported accessing waitlist services. Due to the low number of respondents across many service provision categories, the lack of representation of Toronto respondents, the underrepresentation of lower-income respondents, and the significant number of AIP transfer respondents, it is not possible to generalize these findings to the wider Ontario caregiver experience within the OAP.

Given these response rates, descriptive statistics were deemed the most appropriate method for reporting on these interrelated barriers and their collective impact on caregivers. It allowed the researcher to summarize and present the findings of the collected data, and to understand the characteristics, attitudes, options, and experiences of these caregivers. Descriptive analysis identified and ruled out any prevalent trends or patterns in the responses (e.g., average ratings, average wait times), and since many of these barriers were conceptually related, analyzing them collectively and not in isolation was deemed more appropriate.

Data Analysis and Rigour

This study used a mixed-methods sequential (quantitative followed by qualitative) explanatory two-phase design (Creswell et al., 2003). Initially, all data were collected

online via SurveyMonkey and downloaded into Microsoft Excel. All respondents were then sorted by demographic region, starting with the North, then Central, Western, Eastern, and Toronto regions. They were then assigned case numbers in numerical order.

As mentioned above, the survey itself had embedded logic to ensure the validity of the responses. For example, if caregivers indicated that they had not renewed their funding, the logic embedded in the system skipped any questions related to reconciling funds. This made it easy to distinguish between those who had missed the question and those who had no opportunity to answer. The researcher, however, noticed that the logic of one question was overlooked (i.e., whether the respondent's child had received their OAP number). As a result, one respondent was unable to answer questions about OAP services that required an OAP number, making their responses unreliable and precluding their inclusion in the study.

Categorization of Data

After assigning case numbers, a visual inspection of the data excluded four participants (as explained above), leaving 65 respondents. The remaining respondent data were converted into tables (pivot tables) that could be filtered to show responses by selecting specific criteria (e.g., funding received, region). This enabled the researcher to analyze any regional or service-specific trends in the data. Missing data, including skipped questions and those where respondents indicated 'not applicable,' were excluded from the data analysis.

Caregivers of children who had received OAP funding (interim, core-clinical) were identified using table filters in Excel. The data from these respondents were used to

describe their experiences with services, reconciliation (if applicable), and satisfaction with the funding amount(s).

All related data were transferred to a separate tab in the Excel document and placed into tabs under the following headings: demographics, OAP registration, translation/interpretation, wait times, funding questions, satisfaction with private and public ABA providers, satisfaction with services that did not require funding (e.g., URS, ETS, PT, OT), funding renewal, out-of-pocket expenses, distance travelled, open-ended-questions that could be analyzed quantitatively (e.g., age of diagnosis, amount spent out of pocket), and qualitative data (i.e., four open-ended responses related to registration, barriers, strengths and any other OAP comments).

For the open-ended questions that could be analyzed quantitatively, the data were separated and placed in the DATATAB program for analysis (e.g., mean, standard deviation, frequencies) and to create visual representations (e.g., bar charts, tables). DATATAB is an online statistics calculator that does not store any data; the statistics are performed directly in the web browser, with the data remaining on your computer. Caregiver responses regarding the age of diagnosis were converted from years and months to strictly months to determine the mean age of diagnosis. The process was deductive, and many themes that emerged from the data aligned with those identified in the literature review.

In this study, a five-point Likert scale was employed to measure participants' satisfaction with the services. The responses were coded and interpreted based on the mean score as outlined in *Table 1*. The scale ranged from 1 (“very poor” or “very hard”)

to 5 (“excellent/extreme” or “very easy”). The interpretation of the mean scores was categorized as follows: scores from 1.00 to 1.80 were considered “very poor” or “very hard”; 1.81 to 2.60 as “poor” or “hard”; 2.61 to 3.40 as “good” or “okay”; 3.41 to 4.20 as “very good” or “easy”; and 4.21 to 5.00 as “excellent” or “extreme” (related to funded services) or “very easy” (see Table 1). The data were transferred from the table into an Excel formula to calculate the mean.

Table 1.

Likert Scale Interpretation

Likert Legend	
1= Very hard or very poor	1.00-1.80
2= Hard or poor	1.81-2.60
3= Okay or good	2.61-3.40
4= Easy or very good	3.41-4.20
5 = Very easy or excellent/extreme	4.21-5.00

Note. This table presents the interpretation of mean scores derived from a five-point Likert scale used to evaluate service satisfaction.

A descriptive approach was employed to analyze the data collected from survey respondents, which focused on themes related to service navigation and service provision. The information obtained included average wait time for services, satisfaction with the services, and accessibility.

The four open-ended questions were placed in a separate Excel chart and reviewed repeatedly to discover themes. The responses were uploaded to a qualitative data organizer called Delve. The transcripts from these questions were then coded by the researcher into these categories:

- Diagnosis: Any experiences related to obtaining a diagnosis for their child(ren).
- Documentation and systems: Which included experiences with registration and reconciliation as well as the OAP portal.
- Lack of transparency: Lack of communication about the waitlist, no response from OAP providers, broken promises about services.
- Waitlist: Any comments related to the waitlist for core funding.
- Funding Model: This included how and when funding was received, the Determination of Needs process, the strengths and needs of the OAP, and suggestions to improve services for children with ASD.
- Service Provision: Included feedback (positive and negative) on ABA, SLP, OT, and PT.
- Personal expenses: Feedback about out-of-pocket expenses related to their child's services and needs.

Following coding and analysis, the data were deleted from the account, the account was deactivated, and as an extra precaution, a deletion request was submitted through a formal request to Delve.

Coded items and questions from both the qualitative and quantitative data were sorted into the overarching themes found in the literature (i.e., system navigation or service provision). Translation and interpretation services, as well as distance travelled, were two themes that overlapped in both system navigation and provision categories. For example, translation and interpretation services offered during registration were categorized under system navigation; however, services provided by external providers (e.g., ABA, URS) were placed in the service provision category.

System navigation included categories and themes related to OAP registration (including wait times for the OAP numbers) and reconciliation. Two new themes emerged in the system navigation category related to the ease of the registration process, and the other was the Determination of Needs assessment. Service provision was a much larger category, with themes that emphasized frustration with wait times, adequacy of funding, and satisfaction with services. New themes emerged in this category related to the government's failure to fulfill its commitments and its overall lack of transparency. A final category was created to capture overall experiences and thoughts on the OAP. Items that did not fit into the above-mentioned category themes were placed in this category.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the results, a second checker ensured the accuracy of filters (e.g., those who had received funding, regions), means and table calculations. Procedures taken to ensure the input of the survey scores are valid (e.g.,

average wait-time for services, rating of accessibility of services) and reliable, included having a second checker do the following:

- Review and input the data entered in Excel and,
- Analyze and compare the data with the author's data.

The researcher and second checker each ensured that the data from open-ended questions were categorized correctly, and quantitative data were correctly calculated, including means and standard deviations. To ensure the reliability of qualitative data category descriptions and coding, the primary researcher and second checker jointly categorized the open-ended responses for two respondents who had been excluded. They then independently coded the data of five random participants to compare the results and ensure consistency and accuracy of coding.

Chapter 4: Results

Demographics

The study sample consisted of 65 caregivers, including 62 parents, two grandparents, and one individual who chose not to disclose their relationship to the child. All participants had registered their children for the OAP. Notably, 14 respondents (21.54%) had transitioned from the previous Autism Intervention Program (AIP), which offered both direct funding and direct service options based on clinical assessments. In contrast, the OAP provided a combination of need and age-based funding, with a maximum amount of \$65,000 annually. Funding amounts are calculated based partly on the child's age and on caregiver responses to questions asked during the Determination of Needs (DON) phone or video call. This was a marked shift in service provision for former AIP families.

The largest proportion of respondents ($n = 19$, 29.2%) resided in Central Ontario, while the fewest respondents ($n = 5$, 7.7%) were from Toronto. Other regions included the East ($n = 16$, 24.6%), North ($n = 15$, 23.1%), and West ($n = 10$, 15.3%). Except for Toronto, there was a sufficient representation of respondents across Ontario's regions.

Most households consisted of three or more members. The most common household size was four people ($n = 21$, 32.3%), followed by five ($n = 19$, 29.2%) and three ($n = 15$, 23.1%). A small number of families ($n = 6$, 9.2%) reported six or more members, and four respondents (6.2%) reported living in single-adult households.

Household income ranged from under \$20,000 to over \$200,000 annually. The largest income group ($n = 20$, 30.8%) reported earnings between \$100,000 and \$149,000.

Over half of respondents (52.31%) reported household incomes above \$100,000, suggesting the survey may have been more accessible to middle and higher-income families. Conversely, 14 respondents (21.5%) reported incomes below \$60,000, which indicated potential underrepresentation of lower-income households. Demographic information is captured in Table 2 below.

Table 2.

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Respondents

Region	North		West		Central		East		Toronto		Full Sample	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%
	15	23	10	15	19	29	16	25	5	8	65	100
Relationship												
Parent	14	23	9	15	19	31	15	24	5	8	62	95
Grandparent	1	50	0	0	0	0	1	50	0	0	2	3
No Response	0	0	1	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
No. of people in house												
2	1	25	1	25	0	0	1	25	1	25	4	6
3	2	13	2	13	8	53	3	20	0	0	15	23
4	3	14	5	24	6	29	5	24	2	10	21	32
5	8	42	2	11	4	21	4	21	1	5	19	29
6	0	0	0	0	1	50	0	0	1	50	2	3
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	100	0	0	3	5
8 or more	1	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
Household Income												
< \$20,000	1	25	0	0	0	0	3	75	0	0	4	6
\$20,000-39,000	0	0	3	43	3	43	0	0	1	14	7	11
\$40,000-59,000	2	67	0	0	0	0	1	33	0	0	3	5
\$60,000-79,000	3	27	1	9	2	18	4	36	1	9	11	17
\$80,000-99,000	0	0	0	0	3	75	1	25	0	0	4	6
\$100,000-149,000	6	30	2	10	6	30	4	20	2	10	20	32
\$150,000-199,000	1	20	3	60	1	20	0	0	0	0	5	8
>\$200,000	2	22	1	11	2	22	3	33	1	11	9	14

Note. Demographic characteristics of caregivers who responded to the survey.

System Navigation and Service Provision

Analysis of both quantitative and qualitative results revealed several barriers in terms of system navigation and service provision; however, not all feedback was negative. A small minority of respondents identified some strengths of the Ontario Autism Program (OAP). All respondents provided crucial insights into their experiences navigating services for their child.

System Navigation

Barriers to system navigation were significant and included lengthy wait times for diagnosis and their child's OAP number. Areas of increased stress surrounding registration and reconciliation in the OAP, particularly with the lack of transparency regarding funding (e.g., approved expenditures and renewal timelines), were prominent themes. A new theme emerged from the qualitative data regarding the Determination of Needs (DON) process, highlighting the challenges caregivers faced when advocating for their children.

Assessment and Diagnosis

There were substantial differences in reported wait times for autism assessments across Ontario's regions. According to caregiver responses, average wait times were notably longer in Eastern, Northern, and Western regions. Some families reported waiting over a year for a publicly funded assessment, while others opted to pay privately to avoid extended delays. Table 3 presents the distribution of wait times by region. The most common wait periods were between two and six weeks (51.62% combined), which indicated a reasonable wait time for an assessment. However, 12.91% of respondents

reported waiting more than 12 weeks. This is a considerable delay for children for whom early intervention is key, in a system where waitlists are long.

Table 3.

Wait Time for Autism Assessment by Region

Region	Wait Time for Assessment										Total	
	0-2 weeks		>2-4 weeks		>4-6 weeks		>6-12 weeks		>12 weeks		N	%
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
North	2	3.23%	6	9.68%	1	1.61%	3	4.84%	3	4.84%	15	24.19%
Central	3	4.84%	5	8.06%	8	12.9%	3	4.84%	0	0%	19	30.65%
West	3	4.84%	2	3.23%	1	1.61%	1	1.61%	3	4.84%	10	16.13%
East	1	1.61%	1	1.61%	5	8.06%	4	6.45%	2	3.23%	13	20.97%
Toronto	2	3.23%	2	3.23%	1	1.61%	0	0%	0	0%	5	8.06%
Total	11	17.74%	16	25.81%	6	9.68%	11	17.74%	8	12.9%	62	100%

Note: This table represents the wait time for assessment by geographic region.

Among the 62 respondents, those in the Eastern and Northern regions reported the longest delays. Wait time for assessment is a considerable barrier to timely access to services, as proof of diagnosis is required to register for the Ontario Autism Program (OAP). One caregiver shared the experience of being told that they would wait over two years for an assessment through the diagnostic hub or only four months if they paid privately. The family's financial resources impact timely access to diagnosis and services: "If caregivers have private coverage or are willing to spend a lot of money, then the process is quick and, otherwise, it is frustrating and aggravating" (Young et al.,

2020). Several other caregivers shared this sentiment of long waitlists for assessment and diagnosis.

When examining the age of diagnosis for those surveyed, the youngest reported diagnosis age was 12 months, and the oldest was 72 months (6 years). One extreme outlier (diagnosis at 10 ½ years) was excluded from these calculations. The sample size was N = 63, the average age of diagnosis was 38.0 months (just over 3 years), and the standard deviation was 12.9, which showed considerable variability in diagnosis age.

Considering that a diagnosis is required to register with the OAP and the wait-time for core services is several years, a late diagnosis puts many children outside of the range of early intervention services.

OAP Information Dissemination

After their child received an autism diagnosis, most families were informed about the OAP by a professional (40%) or a community provider (23.08%). This suggested that, contrary to the literature, information was being shared by informed professionals and community contacts. A smaller but notable portion (15.38%) of respondents discovered the program independently, which demonstrated that information gaps remain for some families. One caregiver reported receiving a resource package after diagnosis, but no further guidance was provided.

Nearly three-quarters of respondents learned about the OAP within two weeks of diagnosis (Table 4), which can be interpreted as an improvement in information dissemination. However, four respondents (8.33%) in the Central region reported delays

exceeding 12 weeks, pointing towards potential regional disparities in the dissemination of information.

Table 4.

Wait Time to Receive OAP Information by Region

Frequency and Percentage of Wait Times for OAP Information by Geographic Region												
Region	0-2 weeks		>2-4 weeks		>4-6 weeks		>6-12 weeks		>12 weeks		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%
North	1 0	20.83 %	0	0%	1	2.08 %	0	0%	0	0%	11	22.92 %
Central	8	16.67 %	2	4.17 %	1	2.08 %	0	0%	4	8.33 %	15	31.25 %
Toronto	2	4.17%	0	0%	0	0%	1	2.08 %	0	0%	3	6.25%
West	4	8.33%	1	2.08 %	0	0%	1	2.08 %	0	0%	6	12.5%
East	1 1	22.92 %	0	0%	2	4.17 %	0	0%	0	0%	13	27.08 %
Total	3 5	72.92 %	3	6.25 %	4	8.33 %	2	4.17 %	4	8.33 %	48	100%

Note: This table shows the number of weeks participants waited to learn about the Ontario Autism Program.

The speed with which families received OAP information and from whom, should be interpreted cautiously. Of those who responded (N = 48), 14 or 29.17% were enrolled in the former AIP, and all information about their child's transfer would have been communicated to them by their regional providers or notifications through the Ministry of Children, Community and Social Services (MCCSS)/OAP. This may have contributed to the positively skewed lower wait times for OAP information and inflated the number of

respondents who received that information from community contacts or professionals. Although some families reported challenges in receiving communications about the transfer, most AIP families surveyed transitioned relatively seamlessly to the OAP with little disruption to service.

All survey respondents had registered with the OAP. The majority (n = 47; 72.31%) registered online; other, less common registration methods included mail, phone, fax, or through a community agency. One respondent used multiple methods, and another did not answer.

When asked about the time required to complete registration, 28 or 43.08% of caregivers did not answer. The high non-response rate may reflect discomfort, confusion, or difficulty recalling the experience, possibly due to the simplicity or complexity of the task. Based on the data from those who responded (N=37), the registration experience was mixed but tended to support a more straightforward registration process for many. Over half (n = 20; 54.05%) reported completing registration in one to two hours. When asked to share any challenges with registration, a small but notable portion of respondents (9 out of 28 or 32.1%) reported no barriers during the registration process, highlighting a positive aspect of navigating the system. A similar trend was noted in the qualitative data, with 11 caregivers commenting on the ease of the registration process. Others also felt the centralized system was a positive feature of the OAP.

Not all caregivers viewed their OAP registration so positively; 21.62% of caregivers reported that it took more than 24 hours to complete their child's OAP registration, resulting in a challenging process for respondents. Caregiver themes from

the qualitative data supported these challenges, with individuals sharing stories about the system crashing, confusing documentation requirements, and a lack of communication (e.g., being unable to contact anyone with website issues, receiving no information about the status of their child’s application, or experiencing long wait times to receive their child’s OAP number). These data suggested that although many experienced a quick and easy registration process, with many noting no barriers, others found it more complex and challenging.

To further explore potential barriers, caregivers were asked whether they required assistance during the registration process. As shown in Table 5, most (69.23%) did not require assistance, while nearly one-third (29.23%) did, which indicated that registration (and, consequently, services) was not equally accessible to all families.

Table 5.

Frequency and Percentage of Participants Requiring Help with Registration

Did You Require Help with Registration?	Frequency	Percent
No	45	70.31%
Yes	19	29.69%
Total (N)	65	100.00%

Note: This table displays the number of participants who indicated whether they required assistance during the registration process.

Respondents were asked if they were offered interpretation or translation services to explore how accessible the OAP was for newcomers or individuals who did not speak English or French. The data revealed that only 12 caregivers (20.00%) were offered these services, while most respondents (48, 80.99%) were not. Although several caregivers did

not require translation and interpretation services, these results suggest that they are not being offered consistently. This gap during service navigation may delay registration in the Ontario Autism Program for some newcomer families.

Another factor that delayed services was the receipt of their child's Ontario Autism Program registration number (OAP number). Without an OAP number, children cannot access Foundational Family or Urgent Response Services, a program where caregivers are able to self-refer to access short-term consultation and caregiver education sessions. The Entry to School and Caregiver-Mediated Early Years Programs are invitation-only, but caregivers still require their child's OAP number to be eligible to receive an invitation.

Delayed receipt of their child's OAP number was a big concern for some caregivers. Without an OAP Number, their child was not on the waitlist for funding and could not access any of the above services. Caregivers were asked to report on the time between registration and receipt of their child's OAP number. One respondent could not recall, and two respondents (one in the North and another in the East) were still awaiting their OAP number. Table 6 (below) represents the frequency and percentage of reported wait times for each child's OAP number, disaggregated by the participants' geographic region.

Table 6.*Frequency and Percentage of Wait Times for OAP Number by Geographic Region*

Region	0-2 weeks		>2-4 weeks		>4-6 weeks		>6-12 weeks		>12 weeks		Total	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%
North	0	0.00%	2	3.85%	2	3.85%	6	11.54%	2	3.85%	12	23.08%
Central	1	1.92%	3	5.77%	3	5.77%	7	13.46%	3	5.77%	17	32.69%
Toronto	1	1.92%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0.00%	0	0%	1	1.92%
West	3	5.77%	1	1.92%	2	3.85%	1	1.92%	1	1.92%	8	15.38%
East	3	5.77%	0	0%	1	1.92%	4	7.70%	6	11.54%	14	26.92%
Total	8	15.38%	6	11.54%	8	15.39%	18	34.62%	12	23.08%	52	100%

Note. The table above shows wait times for OAP numbers by region.

When examined as a whole, the survey data from the 52 participants reveals notable delays in receiving the number and ultimately accessing services. The largest proportion of respondents ($n=18$, 34.62%) reported wait times exceeding six weeks but within twelve weeks. Furthermore, a substantial 23.08% ($n=12$) of participants indicated wait times of more than 12 weeks. In total, over half of the caregivers (57.7%) experienced wait times exceeding six weeks. In contrast, only a small percentage reported very short waits, with 15.38% ($n=8$) waiting 0-2 weeks and 11.54% ($n=6$) waiting over two but within four weeks.

In the North, there was a concerning absence of immediate access to an OAP number, with 0% of respondents reporting wait times in the '0-2weeks' category. The most prevalent wait time in the North was '>6-12 weeks' ($n=6$, 11.54%), with two caregivers reporting wait times exceeding 12 weeks. Although some short waits were reported ($n=42$ in each of the '>2-4week' and '>4-6 week' categories), for many respondents, delays were common in this region.

Central Ontario had the highest number of responses for analysis (n=17). Similar to the North, longer wait times were prominent, with the highest frequency (n=7, 13.46%) falling in the '>6-12 weeks' category. Three respondents in this region experienced waits over 12 weeks, and again, like the North, some short waits were reported in the '0-2week' (n=1) and '>2-4 week' categories (n=3). Most children in this region waited over 6 weeks for their OAP number.

Toronto had an extremely small sample size (N=1), the single caregiver reported a wait time of '0-2weeks' (1.92%). Due to this extremely small sample, it is not possible to draw any generalizable conclusions about wait times for OAP numbers in this area, highlighting a limitation in regional representation for this specific variable.

Those in the West appeared to have a split distribution of wait times, with half the respondent's reporting waits under 4 weeks (n=4, 7.69%) and the other half of the respondents reporting waits over 4 weeks. The highest frequency for the West was in the shortest '0-2week' category (n=3, 5.77%)

Children in Eastern Ontario had the highest percentage of respondents who experienced the longest wait times, with 11.54% (n=6) reporting wait times over 12 weeks for their child's OAP number. This suggested that families in this region were particularly impacted by prolonged delays to OAP services, even though a few (n=3, 5.77%) also experienced short waits.

Overall, the registration process experience varied widely. While many caregivers found the process straightforward, others described it as time-consuming and difficult, citing issues with the website and required documentation. The wait time to receive their

child's OAP number also hindered their child's access to timely services. It illustrated the extent to which wait times constitute a barrier to OAP access and identified notable regional disparities, especially in the East, with those experiences.

OAP contacts and service providers were inconsistently offering translation and interpretation, likely increasing barriers to system navigation for newcomers and ESL families. For families who are already navigating complex challenges, an arduous registration process can be a big obstacle when navigating services.

Determination of Needs (DON)

The DON is an online or telephone-based interview designed to assess the needs of children with autism. Caregivers respond to a comprehensive set of questions about their children's abilities across various domains (e.g., language, social, self-help) to determine funding amounts.

When examining the qualitative data about the DON, interestingly, not all feedback was negative. One caregiver viewed the DON process more favourably, noting that it could result in adequate funding for those who were able to navigate the process effectively. However, the overwhelming majority of respondents did not have the same perspective.

Caregivers described the DON process as inadequate, impersonal, and not reflective of their children's actual needs. The process was cited as onerous and trivial. Concerns were raised about the qualifications of those conducting the assessments and the lack of individualized consideration for each participant. This sentiment was particularly prevalent among families of 'Legacy Children,' a term used to refer to those

who were part of the previous Autism Intervention Program (AIP) and were transferred to the OAP. These families had previously undergone a different assessment process under the AIP, which was more clinically driven. This created a unique situation where they were able to compare and critique the new processes.

OAP Reconciliation

Twenty-eight individuals shared their experiences regarding the renewal of their Ontario Autism Program (OAP) funding, a process known as OAP Reconciliation. When asked to rate the ease of the renewal process on a Likert scale from 1 (“very hard”) to 5 (“very easy”), the average rating was 1.82, with a standard deviation of 1.60. This low mean score suggests that, on average, participants found the reconciliation process challenging, with considerable variability in their experiences. Figure 1 shows the distribution of responses, which rated reconciliation, with over 80% of respondents who found reconciliation challenging (53% of respondents found reconciliation very hard, and 30% found it hard). The remaining caregivers found reconciliation to be “okay” (4; 15.38%), “easy” (1), and “very easy” (1).

Figure 1.*Ease of Reconciliation*

Note. Scale showing caregiver responses rating the ease of the OAP reconciliation process.

The qualitative data revealed widespread frustration with the funding renewal process. Participants frequently described the application procedures, documentation requirements, and expense reconciliation as stressful, time-consuming, and not user-friendly. The lack of clarity about approved expenditures and the long wait time for funds to be reconciled and renewed were identified as some of the most significant barriers to the OAP. The online portal was often cited as problematic, and the administrative burdens and complexities of OAP registration and reconciliation were strong points of contention among the caregivers surveyed.

The convergence of both data types underscores the need for improvements in the clarity, accessibility, and efficiency of the OAP funding renewal process.

Service Provision

Caregivers were asked to rate the sufficiency and their satisfaction with various types of services available through the OAP and government-funded early intervention programs (e.g., Entry to School, Speech-Language Pathology [SLP]). To explore any accessibility challenges with service provision, caregivers were asked whether they were offered interpretation or translation from their providers and how far they travelled for services.

Barriers to service provision identified from the qualitative data included long waitlists, out-of-pocket expenses, and services that did not adequately meet their children's needs. These shortcomings were attributed to funding inadequacies, a shortage of qualified providers, and age-based eligibility restrictions. Additionally, many respondents expressed the view that the OAP lacked transparency, and the government had not fulfilled its commitments regarding autism services.

Despite these concerns, participants acknowledged several positive aspects of the OAP. These included the existence of a publicly funded service specific to children with autism, access to care coordinators, and the benefits of a centralized system.

Funding

A total of 44 (67.69%) families reported that their children had received some form of funding (i.e., interim, core-clinical). Twenty-one of those 44 families (almost one-third of all survey respondents and close to half of those who received funding) reported that their child had received core clinical funding. However, close to half (n=10) included children who had transferred from the previous AIP. This is noteworthy because

these children received services under the previous AIP (a clinical decision and need-based formula); most transferred to receive OAP core funding rather seamlessly and did not go on the waitlist.

Just over half (n=11) of the 21 respondents who received core funding had been on the OAP waitlist and received services solely from the OAP, representing just 16.92% of those who were surveyed. This small sample of those who received core clinical services solely from the OAP is reflective of the most significant and most noteworthy concern of OAP families surveyed: the long waitlists for funding. This aligns with current estimates, which indicate that approximately 28% of children (nearly one-third) eligible for the OAP are receiving core funding (Open Council, 2024). When asked about the most substantial barrier to the OAP, the predominant theme, mentioned most frequently and with the most passion, was the long waitlist.

Most caregivers (44, 67.69%) who responded had indicated that their child had received some form of funding (e.g. interim funding, core clinical). Interim funding was provided to families on the waitlist who had registered for the OAP before April 2021 and had not received core funding. It was a one-time annual payment of \$20,000 to \$22,000 for children under 6 years old or \$3,000 to \$5,500 for those 6 years old and over. This funding was available by invitation only and could be renewed only once (in the second round). The intention was to offer some financial support while families waited for core clinical services. Two children, representing 4.55%, received one round of interim funding and 19 children, representing 43.18%, received a second round. These one and two-time payments do not seem to be available to families any longer. One

family reported that their child had not received any funding for over a year, and another reported that their child had lost gains made due to wait times for core funding.

Almost half of those who reported receiving funding (N=21; 47.74%) had received core clinical funding. Eighteen, or 40.90% of those who received funding (27.69% of all respondents) reported that their child had received more than one type of funding in addition to core clinical services (e.g., interim funding, AIP).

Even for caregivers with funding, finances can be a barrier to accessing treatment for their child. In 2015, 80% of caregivers said paying out of pocket, and 77% said the province's lack of coverage posed significant barriers to treatment (Jones, 2015). In 2019, the McLaughlin and Schneider report found that 44% of those who responded said funding was not enough for the amount of ABA therapy their child required. This survey found that respondents (N=26) overwhelmingly felt that funding was insufficient to support their child's needs. Twenty-three individuals (or 88.46%) stated that it was insufficient, with only three (11.54%) caregivers who rated it as satisfactory.

For most respondents, the amount of funding was considered inadequate, a finding supported by the qualitative data. Themes revealed caregivers' dissatisfaction with the insufficiency of the funding provided and their perception that the age-based funding model was discriminatory. One caregiver reported a 70% reduction in funding from the previous AIP. Many others believed that funding should be a clinical decision, based on individual need. Many families lamented the poor funding and attempted to supplement it with their own funds or stretch the funding to last the year.

Services

From the data collected, caregivers reported that service providers offered translation and interpretation services to a small minority (2, or 8.33%), while a substantial proportion (22, 91.67%) reported they were not offered. Providing interpretation and translation during service provision enables caregivers to make informed decisions about their child's therapies. Khanlou 2017 found that “communication barriers made it difficult for mothers to recognize the need for several providers’/service agencies’ simultaneous involvement in providing care to their children.” As the literature showed, the oversight in omitting this option for families could widen the service provision gap for those children.

Of the 30 individuals who responded to the question about how they spent their funding, most reported that their child received more than one type of service. Twenty of those included ABA, and 13 included respite services; only five respondents indicated that they accessed services solely for speech-language pathology (SLP) and occupational therapy (OT). The complex therapy needs of some children on the spectrum could influence the diversity of services sought. These results suggest that caregivers are seeking a combination of strategies to help increase their child's developmental trajectory (ABA, SLP) as well as seeking parental relief from the many challenges of raising a young child with autism.

When examining the strengths of the program from the qualitative data, caregivers reportedly appreciated the flexibility in funding. This allowed them to allocate resources toward a range of therapies, such as speech-language pathology, psychology

and occupational therapy, rather than being limited to Applied Behaviour Analysis (ABA), instilling a sense of hope for the program's potential.

Of the caregivers who shared how they found their child's ABA provider (N = 26), most did so independently (9, or 34.62%). Other sources included recommendations from multiple sources and another parent of a child with Autism (4; 15.38%). A few found their provider through professionals and the approved providers list online (2; 7.69%), while only one was referred by a friend or family member. Four respondents (15.38%) reported not having a provider, which is supported by the qualitative data where caregivers indicated they had trouble finding services for older children, appropriate services (e.g., eligible social skills groups, services in French) and ABA services in general. When examining Francophone services provided by family physicians in Ontario, Gauthier (2015) noted that "Actively offering services in French should not be the responsibility of the patient." Even those awaiting funding indicated they would not be able to find services close to home, if at all. This would support what is found in the literature, which indicates that a lack of qualified professionals in rural, remote, and northern communities frequently results in long waitlists for services (Harrington et al., 2013).

From the smaller number of caregivers who responded (N = 22), 16 or 72.73% had no more than two providers; five or 22.73% had three to five providers; and only one respondent (4.55%) had more than five providers. These results could suggest that caregivers are satisfied with their child's ABA provider(s), or they may represent limited options for ABA providers, making it difficult to find a new one.

Satisfaction with ABA providers was divided into two categories: public and private providers. Twenty-two caregivers rated their public ABA providers on a scale of one (“very poor”), to five (“excellent”). Most caregivers (n=17, 77.27%) rated these services well (i.e., from “good” to “excellent”). However, five caregivers (22.73%) viewed their experience with public ABA in a harsher light by rating those services as “poor” or “very poor”. This could be related to sentiments discovered in the qualitative data, where parents shared frustrations with finding therapies for older children, those with more complex needs and those with fewer needs. Dissatisfaction with public providers could be due to their association with the insufficiencies of the OAP itself. Often, public providers are tasked with implementing other programs within the OAP, such as Foundational Family Services and Urgent Response services. Based on caregiver responses, they were more satisfied with services from their child’s public ABA providers than their private ones.

When asked the same question about their private ABA providers, the response was mixed. Thirteen caregivers, or 50% of respondents (N = 26), found the service to be poor or very poor, and the other 50% found it to be average (n = 10) or above average (n = 3). When reviewing the qualitative data, some caregivers suggested that the OAP funding model primarily benefited ABA providers and the private market. The lack of sufficient oversight, questionable billing practices and accountability were mentioned.

Only six respondents reported accessing Urgent Response Services (URS), while 24 had accessed Foundational Family Services (FFS); both services are available to any child with an Ontario Autism Program (OAP) number. Of those caregivers who received

URS (N=6), only one respondent rated this service as “very good”, over 80% rated the service as “poor” (33.33%) and “very poor” (50%). The overall Likert score was 1.83 (standard deviation 1.63), indicated a “very poor” overall rating. One family shared that the service only being available during business hours was a barrier, and the URS respite program was being offered at centers that are too far from home. Foundational Family Services also received a poor rating, with a mean score of 2.25 (standard deviation 1.91) on the Likert scale regarding satisfaction with those services. One respondent found that this program relied too heavily on virtual service options. These findings coincided with those of McLaughlin and Schneider (2019) where 42% of caregivers stated lack of control over the time and location of services was a big challenge.

Ten respondents had received services through the Entry to School (ETS) program, which also requires an OAP number but is invitation-only and limited to children 6 years old and under who are entering school for the first time. Half of all respondents rated this program as insufficient for their child’s needs, 40% rated the program as very poor, and 10% as “poor”. The other half of the respondents rated the program as good (30%) and “very good” (20%). When converting the Likert scale rating, an overall mean score of 2.3 (standard deviation 3.16) was obtained, indicating a poor overall rating with high variability in responses, as noted by the split among caregivers who found the program suited their child’s needs and those who found it severely lacking. One caregiver noted that, although they were never able to use the program, it appeared to be beneficial. Another shared that they could see the benefit of the program,

but it resulted in the cessation of early years 1:1 programming for speech and occupational therapies for their child.

Only four respondents reported receiving a caregiver-mediated early years program, which is also available only by invitation to children up to 4 years old; however, the survey questions did not include a satisfaction rating scale for this service. Based on the qualitative data, some caregivers were upset that they were expected to become therapists for their children, citing the pressures and time constraints of trying to do so, and some indicated that this was not a suitable substitution for funded services.

Overall satisfaction with these OAP services (excluding core funding and caregiver-mediated early years programs) is presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7.*Satisfaction with OAP Services by Region*

Region	North		West		Central		East		Toronto		Full Sample	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	N	%
Foundational Family Services												
Extreme	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Good	0	0	1	50	1	50	0	0	0	0	2	3
Good	2	25	1	13	2	25	2	25	1	13	8	12
Poor	2	29	0	0	2	29	2	29	1	14	7	11
Very Poor	2	29	1	14	2	29	2	29	0	0	7	11
Urgent Response Services												
Extreme	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Good	1	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
Good	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Poor	0	0	1	50	0	0	0	0	1	50	2	3
Very Poor	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	100	0	0	2	3
Entry to School Program												
Extreme	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Good	0	0	1	50	0	0	0	0	1	50	2	3
Good	0	0	1	33	1	33	0	0	1	33	3	5
Poor	0	0	0	0	1	100	0	0	0	0	1	2
Very Poor	1	25	0	0	1	25	2	50	0	0	4	6

Note. Respondents who received these OAP services rated how well these services met their child's needs.

Finally, caregivers were asked about their experiences with other government-funded therapies (e.g., early intervention services) that were not part of the OAP but are typically included to support their autistic child's growth and development. Questions were explicitly asked about speech, occupational and physiotherapy. Caregivers were asked to use the Likert scale to rate whether or not these services were sufficient to support their child's needs.

More than half of respondents (35 out of 65; 53.85%) reported access to speech services (SLP), and nearly half (27; 41.53%) reported receiving occupational therapy (OT). In contrast, only 10 respondents, or 15.38%, reported on physiotherapy (PT). Of those respondents, only 11 shared their ratings of SLP services, seven shared their ratings of OT services, and two shared their ratings of PT services.

The mean rating of SLP services was 2.18 on the Likert scale, with an overall rating of "poor." However, a standard deviation of 2.00 indicates variability in experiences, with seven caregivers rating SLP services as poor or very poor and four rating them as good or excellent.

OT services showed lesser variation in experiences, with six respondents rating these services as poor or very poor and only one providing a rating of very good. The mean was 1.86, and the standard deviation was 1.6, with an overall rating on the Likert scale of poor for the adequacy of this service. One family reported limited access to SLP and OT services in the North, and another noted that the service model lacked parental involvement. Another family faced a long waitlist for government-funded OT and SLP services, which they found frustrating.

When asked about the adequacy of physiotherapy services, both respondents (N = 2) rated them as poor and very poor (mean = 1.5, SD = 2.24, overall rating: very poor). Again, given the small number of respondents, these findings cannot be generalized. In examining the qualitative data, one caregiver noted that there was no availability for services in their community for ABA, speech, OT and PT.

Lack of Transparency and Follow Through

The lack of transparency and communication from the government was a recurring theme during qualitative analysis. Information about programs, eligibility, and waitlists was often sought from unofficial sources such as Facebook groups. Caregivers expressed frustration over the lack of clear timelines, information about their child's position on waitlists, and the responsiveness of the OAP contacts (e.g., care coordinators). Another strong theme that emerged from the qualitative data was the government's broken promise of eliminating the waitlist and frustration with the fact that, under the current model, their children will not receive funding for several years.

Financial Pressures

Many caregivers (44, 67.69%) reported incurring out-of-pocket expenses for their child's services. Over 12 months, some families reported spending upwards of \$25,000 per year, with three families who shared that they paid between \$40,000 and \$50,000 during the same period. The amount spent ranged from zero dollars to \$50,000 per year. Those with older children (7 years and older) reported spending over \$100,000 since diagnosis. The qualitative data is similar, with one caregiver of a 17-year-old stating that they have spent almost \$300,000 since diagnosis. This family reported they had just received funding and will have to give it back because no suitable approved therapies are available.

Many families shared their frustration with out-of-pocket expenses as their child awaited core funding. They stated that they know early intervention is key and are paying for therapy themselves when they can. One family reported selling their cottage to fund

early intervention. This suggests that caregivers believe services provided do not adequately meet their child's needs (e.g., insufficient funding, long waitlists), leading them to invest their own money to ensure timely access to therapies for their children.

Geographic Barriers

For many, transportation can be a significant barrier when accessing funded services, particularly for those who reside in remote or underserved geographic regions. Caregivers were asked to report the distances they travelled to access OAP and other funded services (e.g. SLP, OT, PT).

Travel in the North was predominantly less than 50 km for all services (except for diagnosis), which is noteworthy. During the literature review, it was found that individuals in remote areas typically experience longer travel times. Some also reported receiving services in their homes or virtually, highlighting alternative delivery models in remote or sparsely serviced regions. Caregivers in this region reported extended travel for diagnosis, with 30.00% travelling over 150 km for their child's initial assessment. Although services may be geographically close, seeking assessment could result in significant geographic barriers for those in the North.

The Central region showed a range of travel distances for C-MEY, ABA, SLP, OT and PT (no caregivers reported accessing URS in this region). A majority (59.46%) reported travelling under 50km, and 24.32% reported travelling 50-100km. There was one (2.70%) instance of travel in the 101-150 km range. Additionally, some of these services were provided virtually and in-home, accounting for 15.51%. When it came to assessment, 53.85% travelled 50-100km and 46.15% travelled under 50km, indicative of

a divided travel experience. Overall, the data lean toward fewer geographic barriers for some in Central Ontario.

In the West, in-home and virtual services were most frequently used (50%), and 40.90% reported travelling under 50 km. Others travelled further distances, with 9.10% travelling 101-150km for most services. When travelling for diagnostic services, most (55.56%) reported travelling under 50 km, 22.22% travelled 101-150km, and 11.11% travelled 50-100km and received assessment at home. Overall, services appeared most accessible in the Western region. Like other regions, there are still some people travelling further distances for a diagnosis.

Travel in the East was clustered. Many (56.42%) indicated short distances (less than 50 km), fewer (17.95%), reported mid-range travel (50-100 km), and a smaller number of respondents (15.38%) reported long-distance travel (greater than 150 km). In-home and virtual services were also reported by 10.25% of respondents in the East. Eleven people in this region shared their travel time for assessment. 45.45% travelled under 50km, 36.36% 50-100km, and 9.09% over 150km and virtually. Those in the East had varied experiences with travel, but more children received services close to, or in, their homes. Similar to other regions, travel for assessment was longer, with one caregiver reportedly travelling over 150km for their child's assessment.

Lastly, the distance travelled in the Toronto region was almost exclusively short distances, with all reported trips being less than 50 km. Some reported in-home and virtual services, and there is no recorded travel beyond 50 km for respondents in this area. All of those who reported distance travelled for diagnostic services were under

50km. The findings from this small survey sample indicate that services could be more accessible for those closer to the city, as was found in the research (Harrington et al, 2013; Khanlou, 2014).

When travel times were aggregated across all regions, most respondents reported travelling under 50 kilometres to access most services (except diagnostic services), demonstrating that for most caregivers, services are located nearby. However, qualitative data showed that caregivers did not feel virtual options for service were suitable for their child. Table 8 represents all distances travelled for all services across all regions in Ontario.

Table 8.

Location or Distance Travelled for Services

Location/Distance Travelled for Services	Assessment	ETS	CMEY	URS	ABA	SLP	OT	PT
In home	1	0	4	3	6	3	5	0
Virtual	3	0	4	1	0	3	1	0
>50km	25	6	10	0	20	29	21	6
50-100KM	12	2	2	1	4	5	5	1
101-105KM	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
>150KM	4	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
N	47	8	21	6	32	42	33	9

Note: This table shows the location or distance travelled for various services.

More than half (53.19%) of caregivers reported travelling under 50km for diagnosis, and an additional four (8.51%) participants reported receiving their child's assessment at home or online. Those travelling 50 kilometres or more represented 38.30% of the caregivers who responded. This finding is significant because caregivers

cannot register their child for the OAP without a diagnosis. One of the revisions to the OAP included the investment in diagnostic hubs in all five Regions to increase accessibility and address the waitlist. Some families are travelling a notable distance during that first step in obtaining that help for their child, encountering geographic barriers, resulting in service delays for their children.

Some caregivers (n =22, 18.97%) reported travelling 50 to 100 kilometres for ABA, SLP, and OT services. A significant majority of caregivers (n = 117, 65.52%) reported travelling under 50 kilometres for the services mentioned in the above table, indicating fewer geographical barriers to therapies, specialized programs, and funded services. Furthermore, the provision of some of these services, either virtually or in-home accounting, for just a little over 15% of respondents, eliminated the need for travel. It appears that for many, service locations are more localized.

Chapter 5: Discussion, Conclusions, and Recommendations

Initial steps in the OAP navigation were challenging, as caregivers reported difficulties in seeking services promptly and in proximity to their homes. For some caregivers, these time delays started when seeking their child's assessment for diagnosis. The trend continued with some spending great lengths of time registering their child for the OAP and waiting to receive their number. Wait times for diagnosis, OAP information, and to receive their child's OAP number were problematic. Over half of those who responded waited longer than six weeks, with a substantial proportion waiting over three months to receive their child's OAP number.

Those who were fortunate enough to receive funding stated that the reconciliation process was stressful, time-consuming, and not user-friendly. This is similar to the findings of McLaughlin and Schneider (2019), where 25% of families reported frustration when dealing with paperwork and managing services. One caregiver believed that the DON and reconciliation processes were so time-consuming that they should be financially compensated.

There was a strong sentiment that the government had failed to deliver on its commitment to provide timely and adequate support for children with autism. The impact of these delays on early intervention and children's developmental progress was a primary concern. Of particular concern was the delay in the assessment process, which ultimately delays services. The delay in obtaining a diagnosis is particularly discouraging, considering the government doubled its investments in diagnostic hubs (Government of Ontario, 2025).

Generally, most caregivers expressed a deep sense of disappointment, frustration, and anger about the OAP. When asked to note any strengths of the OAP, a high number (18 out of 30) reported none, a strong indicator of dissatisfaction with the program. However, some caregivers commended the availability of a centralized system and online portal for their ease of access, with a notable number finding the registration process straightforward. Nevertheless, some others cited the online system as problematic (e.g., not saving or losing information uploaded).

Several caregivers identified inadequate support and insufficient funding as major obstacles. Parents deemed the funding as insufficient and discriminatory due to its age-based formula, which aligns with the themes that emerged from the qualitative data. Almost all who responded indicated that funding was problematic. Most stated that the waitlist to receive funding for core services was the most challenging barrier to the OAP, as they spent their own money to ensure their child received early intervention. Caregivers were critical of an age-based funding model instead of a needs-based one. Many caregivers described the services and funding available for their children as insufficient or poor. With the high cost of therapy, the funding is not enough to meet their child's needs. However, their determination to provide the best for their children despite funding challenges is truly inspiring.

On the one hand, some caregivers appreciated the broader scope of therapies now eligible for funding, noting it as a strength of the OAP. However, others were disappointed with the loss of specific funding categories (e.g., tuition, respite) as eligible expenses.

The qualitative data revealed caregiver concerns about the lack of support for older children and those with complex needs. Some carers felt that the OAP was geared towards early intervention and did not adequately address the needs of older children or those with more complicated or evolving needs. In contrast, others cited the inclusion of these early years' services as a strength of the current model.

Caregivers who had received funding from the AIP lamented the previous program, which was a needs-based funding model based on a clinical assessment completed by a psychologist. One caregiver wanted to return to the government in place before the current one was elected. Some caregivers felt the current OAP was worse, less flexible, and had created more barriers than the previous AIP. This trend was to be expected given the high number of respondents who had transferred from that program.

The waitlist was cited as the most prevalent concern among caregivers surveyed. Many caregivers were upset because their child would be too old for early intervention by the time they received funding. Others were despondent because, despite their best efforts, they could not personally finance their child's therapies. Some expressed frustration that they were expected to become therapists for the child(ren) and then accountants when tasked with an unclear and time-consuming reconciliation process. Many caregivers were bothered by the government's lack of transparency regarding the waitlist numbers, their child's position and when core funding could be expected. The current model of the OAP has resulted in increased stressors and pressures for caregivers who are already at risk for higher rates of depression and burnout.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

Targeted efforts to include those from remote communities were successful, with a strong representation of caregivers from Northern Ontario. Other areas of Ontario were also similarly represented; however, the sample from the Toronto area was significantly lacking, which made determining any region-specific trends unlikely. The small sample size in many categories (e.g., Urgent Response Services, Entry to School) also precluded any generalizations.

Caregivers who responded to this survey represented a higher socio-economic demographic as per their self-report on income. Those responding needed access to a device (e.g., phone, tablet) and an elementary understanding of the English language, which resulted in the survey being less accessible to lower-income families, caregivers who speak other languages, and individuals with learning, cognitive, and/or intellectual disabilities. Furthermore, most caregivers did not require translation services or help with registration, which likely demonstrated familiarity with system navigation and service provision.

This familiarity likely stems from the fact that almost one-fifth of those surveyed were caregivers to Legacy Children (children had transferred from the previous AIP, which was a clinical need-based model). These caregivers frequently compared the current OAP with the previous program, which may have affected the satisfaction ratings for services like Foundation Family Services and Urgent Response Services, as well as satisfaction with funding amounts. However, those caregivers who had not received AIP

services echoed these sentiments about the insufficiency of funding and inadequacy of services like URS.

Because many Legacy children were older, they would not qualify for the Caregiver-Mediated or Entry to School Program, resulting in lower response rates for this set of questions. Alternatively, over two-thirds of caregivers reported that their child had received some type of funding and just shy of one-third had received core funding. This is not a typical experience for caregivers, when current estimates indicate that only one-fifth of eligible children have received core funding (Jones, 2024).

Time was a limitation of this survey. The extended time the survey was made available online delayed the analysis of the results. The overall survey was quite lengthy, with many respondents skipping or choosing not to answer questions, perhaps due to fatigue and the time spent completing the survey. The volume of data obtained from the many questions took a lot of time to sort, code and analyze.

The survey logic was missed for one question, and this researcher failed to ask about satisfaction with Caregiver-Mediated Early Years (CMEY) programs and distance travelled for Foundational Family Services (FFS). However, since most regional hubs and service providers offer URS and CMEY, the distance travelled for those programs would be similar to that for most FFS programs.

The title of the paper indicates bias in the information seeking. Although this research tried to remain as neutral as possible, the wording of the questions and the title of the survey set the tone for the responses. Based on the literature review and media reports, the assumption from the start was that the program was not performing well and

would not be viewed favourably by caregivers. This proved to be true; however, surprisingly, there were some aspects of the OAP that caregivers viewed favourably (registration, using funding for therapies other than ABA).

Limitations of this methodology include the small sample size and the amount of data analysis required (quantitative and qualitative). The minimal number of responses to some questions does not allow for inferences about the larger population, and although descriptive statistics accurately described the experience of the small sample size, the ability to infer findings to larger populations was limited.

At the time this survey was launched, the OAP had recently introduced Caregiver-Mediated and Entry to School programs for younger children who had not received core clinical funding. While all efforts were made to ensure the distinction between these new services, some families may have been confused and overwhelmed by the different service streams, which potentially affected the accuracy of their responses.

A mixed-methods design provided an abundance of information from both sources. This type of design allowed this researcher to answer, “confirmatory and explanatory questions simultaneously” (Dawadi et al., 2021), by gaining further understanding of the complex dynamics of system navigation and provision within the OAP. These types of data sources lead to an increased understanding of the “research issue through the use of separate yet dialectically related approaches” (Dawadi et al., 2021)

Overall, a stricter timeline, a survey with fewer questions, some phrased better with more attention to detail, and accurate skip logic would have helped the survey's

integrity. Offering the survey in other formats (e.g., different languages, paper copies) and targeting agencies that serve marginalized communities may have reduced the heterogeneity of respondents. A more inclusive sample from those who live in urban areas, are from diverse backgrounds, and economic statuses would have helped to capture more diverse experiences.

Conclusion

The barriers to accessing the Ontario Autism Program were substantial. Caregivers described the emotional toll of waitlists from developmental screening to receiving services and funding. Many found funding and services to be substandard and not based on their child's needs or clinical assessment. Those surveyed reported increased stress and financial pressure because of the OAP's failures. The lack of transparency about the waitlist was the most resounding theme.

For those who had received funding, the Determination of Needs process and problems with expense reconciliation proved worrisome and time-consuming. Instead of relying on the diagnostic assessments required for OAP registration (which some families wait several months or years to receive), caregivers must attend a DON interview every year, which can take up to four hours for some caregivers to complete (Jones, 2024). Caregivers experienced the DON as upsetting and unnecessary. For caregivers whose children lack skills in many of the domains assessed, this can be quite upsetting. For those new to Ontario and who speak languages other than English or French, these barriers would be magnified. Caregivers are not being offered translation and interpretation services consistently, indicative of a large gap in service provision.

Offering these services allows caregivers to make informed choices and mitigates the likelihood that some disenfranchised populations fall through the cracks.

While some caregivers championed the flexibility of funding that included other therapies (e.g., occupational, speech), others were upset that the funding expenses no longer included respite (covered under interim funding) or school tuition (covered under the previous AIP childhood budgets). In the same way, while some caregivers appreciated the agency over their child's treatment, they were overwhelmed by the DON and reconciliation processes. Some felt they should be paid for the time spent completing these processes.

Although the open-ended questions were a robust source of information, the options for caregivers to provide information proved challenging to code. Also, the skip logic embedded in the online survey could have been better programmed to limit the unreliable responses from the two participants excluded in the Eastern Region. The process of filtering and categorizing the questions was also time-consuming due to the large amount of data that needed to be captured.

This study aimed to quantify these experiences to increase the breadth of knowledge about caregivers' experiences with the OAP. Previous research involving caregivers of children with autism had been primarily qualitative (Gentles et al., 2022; McLaughlin & Schneider, 2019). A mixed-methods design is a complementary approach intended to illustrate and clarify the barriers identified in prior research, focus groups, and advisory panels (Dawadi et al., 2021). By quantifying the barriers to program access

across the province, it was possible to gauge the extent to which services and supports are lacking for specific Ontarian populations.

These findings have critical implications for policy and service delivery. Prolonged wait times can delay crucial early interventions, exacerbate family stress, and potentially impact the developmental outcomes for children with autism. The observed regional disparities suggest a need for targeted resource allocation and strategic planning to address bottlenecks in specific geographic areas. Further research with larger, more representative regional samples, particularly for Toronto, would be beneficial to confirm these patterns and pinpoint the specific causes of these regional differences.

When the government came into power in 2018, the waitlist (which they promised to eliminate) was approximately 23,000 (Crawley, 2019). Currently, 14,113 children are receiving core funding (Jones, 2024). The initial target of eliminating the waitlist was lofty, but it would have helped children receive evidence-based early intervention services. It would also have alleviated the financial burdens of supporting the next generation of adults who did not receive timely intervention.

In June 2024, there were just over 73,000 children awaiting core funding, which means many of these children will not receive funding until they are 6 or older (Jones, 2024). The sentiments from caregivers highlight this failure, as many expressed frustrations with the government's broken promises, the lack of transparency about the waitlist and missed opportunities for early intervention. The financial and emotional impact of these failures has left caregivers stressed, burned out and feeling hopeless about a system that seems riddled with obstacles to delay service.

The OAP lacks stability: the minister overseeing the autism portfolio has changed five times since the OAP was created, and the program itself has experienced four major revisions (Jones, 2022). The ever-changing nature of this program, along with the lack of clarity, makes service provision challenging to navigate even for those who are embedded in the field. The waitlist continues to grow, and the future financial impact on the province when these children, who did not receive timely intervention, become adults will likely be substantial. The Pay Now or Pay Later report sounded the alarm back in 2007, and it seems that more than 17 years later, these recommendations continue to be ignored. Meanwhile, caregivers continue to feel overburdened and unsupported, and ultimately, children with autism endure the consequences of a broken system.

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